

IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE IN WRITING FOR NEWSPAPERS

This article is about a number specific characteristic of the language which is used for printed media. It is given very important points of used language and given some suggestions for young journalists.

Key words: language, journalism, mass media, journalistic language, media language.

Language is especially important in journalism. Language is involved with the precise presentation of words and phrases in writing. It contains abbreviations, capitalization, compounding, and other printed language features.

The language used in journalism to present the most recent and up-to-date facts to the public in the simplest, easiest, and most unbiased manner is referred to as journalistic language. Journalism is a crucial kind of communication in which we spread news, information, and knowledge to a wide number of people. It is vital to employ straightforward and basic language for this goal. That is why it is also known as people's language and mass communication language. Here is given some important characteristics of journalistic language.

- **Simple and Easy-** simple and easy language is required for journalism since the main objective of journalism is to enlighten the general public, literate and illiterate alike, which cannot be accomplished without simple and easy language, which is also a key quality of journalistic language.
- **Unbiased-** in journalistic language, we impart knowledge and send data without any expression or personal sentiments; for example, news on television is delivered without the newscaster's own perspective (who reads the news in news bulletin) Reporters at newspapers do not include their sentiments and feelings when writing a report on an incident.
- **Brevity-** Brevity denotes "shortness." We compose news and reports in journalistic style to be succinct and to the point, with no extraneous information.
- **Broadness-**the broadness of journalistic language distinguishes it from other languages. This indicates that journalistic language may describe all themes and their difficulties, whether they are social, religious, political, or educational. As we can see in

newspapers, newspapers cover all themes like as political, social, religious, showbiz, criminal, business, and so on, but other languages just cover a subset of their concerns.

- **Seriousness**-unlike in literary language, facts are expressed in journalistic language in a serious manner.
- **Awareness**- the primary goal of reporting language is to transmit and impart knowledge and information to a big group of individuals in their current state. As a result, the quality of reporting language raises public awareness and encourages individuals to address their own issues.
- **Communication Area**-because journalistic language is intended for the entire public, it has a limitless communication area. As a result, it is straightforward and easy to grasp for the general public.
- **Objectivity**- to be objective, explain an event or item "as it is," without embellishment or extraneous details. This is also an essential aspect of journalistic language.
- **Media Language**- journalistic language is intended for the general public. Mass communication, on the other hand, refers to communicating with a huge number of individuals. In summary, journalistic language is an essential source of mass communication, which is why it is referred to as the language of media
- **Realism**-realism refers to genuineness and actuality. Things are reported in a realistic manner in journalistic terminology.
- Journalistic language represents all social classes. It also reflects all sorts of individuals because newspapers are read by people of different socioeconomic backgrounds.
- **Politeness**- in journalism, politeness of language is required in order to catch the attention of the general public. Otherwise, people would not pay attention to complex words.
- **Grammar**-correct grammar usage is essential in journalistic language; otherwise, it will leave a negative impression on readers. Proper and accurate use of tenses such as past, present, and future is also essential.

- **Avoid Difficult and Unfamiliar Words-** we do not employ complicated and new words in journalistic language for public comprehension.
- **Avoid Difficult Terms-** journalism requires plain and straightforward language. And a journalist takes care of this element by using simple language and avoiding difficult phrases while producing a report since he or she realizes that the report is for everyone, not just one group, so he or she transforms sophisticated and tough terminology into simple ones.
- **Short Phrases-** because it is intended for everyone, journalistic language is built on short and simple sentences.

To sum up, the language used to present the most recent and up-to-date facts to the public in the simplest, easiest, and most unbiased manner is referred to as journalistic language. Language is involved with the precise presentation of words and phrases in writing. Journalism is a crucial kind of communication in which we spread news, information, and knowledge to a wide number of people.

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